

COMPAS

Checking on Mental Health
Providing Alternatives to Suicide

COMPAS Program Training Manual

© Hasking, Chiu, Robinson, Coleman, Marsh, Wheeler, & McEvoy. (2025).

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Acknowledgment of Country

In the spirit of reconciliation, we acknowledge the Traditional Custodians of Country throughout this continent and their connections to land, sea, and community.

We pay our respect to Elders past and present and extend that respect to all Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander peoples today.

Acknowledgement of Lived Experience

We acknowledge the unique insights and knowledge provided by people with lived and living experiences of mental health concerns and suicidal thoughts and behaviours.

We recognise their incredible strength in sharing their diverse experiences and the inspiration and empowerment this fosters.

We value and champion the essential role of lived experience voices in all aspects of research, practice, advocacy, outreach, and policy work.

Value Statement

COMPAS was created to enable person-centred, strengths-focused support to meet university students' needs of enhanced wellbeing. We acknowledge that everyone is unique and is an expert in their own experience.

A Note About Language

The language we use when talking about suicide is important. Inaccurate or harmful language can alienate individuals, perpetuate negative stereotypes, and maintain stigma. We avoid terms like “successful suicide”, “unsuccessful suicide”, “committed suicide”, or “failed suicide” because they present suicide as a desirable outcome, link suicide with crime, and glamourise suicide attempts. Instead, we use inclusive, respectful, and non-stigmatising language, like “died by suicide”, “took their life”, “suicided”, “suicide attempt”, or “non-fatal attempt at suicide.” We recognise that language changes over time and getting used to changes may take some time. Our aim in prioritising more inclusive language is to communicate respect and care for those affected by suicide.

We acknowledge that people value having control and autonomy in their life and so in that vein, people value having control of whether they choose to live or die. The aim of COMPAS is to support people in choosing to live, but we recognise that ultimately this decision rests with the individual.

Learning Objectives

The aim of the COMPAS program is to support students' mental health and reduce incidence of suicide, assist in connecting students to appropriate resources, and evaluate the effectiveness of COMPAS as a suicide prevention program.

Upon completion of this training, you will be able to:

1. Understand suicide risk among university students,
2. Apply your knowledge to supporting students through telehealth,
3. Determine the immediate needs of students and support them to access appropriate resources, and,
4. Reflect on your own practice in supporting students.

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Background

Over 90% of university students experience stress related to finances, health, academics or relationships. Each year, approximately 17% report suicidal ideation, 9% make a suicide plan, and 1% attempt suicide (Mortier et al., 2018).

COMPAS developed from the World Mental Health International College Student Initiative, which studies student mental health and early interventions. First-year students at more than 18 universities worldwide are invited to complete a wellbeing survey assessing mental and physical health. Using data from previous cohorts, our team developed COMPAS (Checking on Mental Health, Providing Alternatives to Suicide) a predictive tool embedded in the survey to identify students at risk of suicidal behaviour in the next 12 months. COMPAS identifies the top 15% at risk and captures 53.06% of students who later report a suicide plan or attempt.

Our team proactively contacts at-risk students to assess their needs and develop personalised support plans, connecting them with university and community services. In crisis situations, we discuss urgent care options such as visiting the emergency department.

An initial evaluation shows COMPAS reduces the likelihood of suicidal behaviour by 41.7% one year after outreach. This impact has earned us the 2022 Curtin Innovation Award (Teaching & Learning), 2023 Professor Helen Christensen Medal from the Society for Mental Health Research for breakthrough research of high national or international significance, 2024 John de Laeter Award for Research Leadership, and the 2025 Suicide Prevention Australia LiFE Award for Innovative Practice and Research in WA.

Developed in collaboration with clinical psychologists, community stakeholders and students with lived experience, COMPAS provides critical support as students navigate university life. This manual will guide you in engaging with students, conducting meaningful conversations and maintaining accurate records.

Welcome to the team we look forward to working with you this semester!

Professor Penelope Hasking and the COMPAS team

Myths and Misconceptions

Myth 1: “Asking a person about suicide will put the idea in their head and encourage them.”

Research has debunked this myth; asking about suicide does not increase risk (Cukrowicz et al., 2010; Deeley & Love, 2010). Rather, it is a critical first step in helping those at risk of suicide. By directly asking if someone is considering suicide in an open and caring way, you are providing an opportunity for them to share how they are feeling and gain support.

Myth 3: “If someone is intent on making a suicide attempt, you cannot stop them.”

This is false. Suicide is preventable. Interventions, support, and resources can help individuals experiencing suicidal thoughts (Suicide Prevention Resource Center, 2004).

Myth 5: “Mental health and suicide risk is low among university students.”

Suicide is a leading cause of death for young Australians aged 15-24. In 2021, 322 Australian young people (aged 18–24) took their own lives (AIHW, 2023). These statistics highlight the need for more support and early interventions, such as COMPAS.

Myth 2: “People who attempt suicidal are selfish or attention seeking.”

There are a range of reasons people suicide including feeling hopeless or emptiness, feeling like a burden, a sense of desperation, or a desire for escape (Nicolopoulous et al., 2017; van Orden et al., 2010). It can also be due to issues accessing support, socioeconomic adversity, interpersonal relationship difficulties, and historical factors such as traumatic life events (Nicolopoulous et al., 2017). Do not dismiss an individual’s distress as attention seeking. All suicidal ideation, attempts, or warning signs should be taken seriously.

Myth 4: “If a person is suicidal, they will always feel that way.”

This is a misconception; suicidal thoughts are not permanent. Rather, they tend to increase when an individual is experiencing stressors. With appropriate support, services, and resources, these thoughts can lessen over time (Nicolopoulous et al., 2017; Suicide Prevention Resource Center, 2004).

Our Approach to Support Students

When talking with students identified as at high-risk, the goal of COMPAS is to listen to each student's personal story, hear their needs, and help link them with appropriate support and resources. COMPAS is **not** about providing psychological treatment or therapy (e.g., CBT).

COMPAS takes a strengths-based approach where we recognise the inherent strengths within each individual and are guided by individuals' potential for change, growth, and resilience. We are driven by respect. This looks like taking a non-judgemental approach, recognising the uniqueness of each individual, and understanding that they are the expert in their own life. We use a collaborative approach wherein we work with the individual and utilise their expertise and experiences.

We recognise that although not every individual will be in a crisis, there will be individuals who may benefit from support and assistance linking in with resources, and referrals. As part of this approach, we developed the COMPAS model to support both students who are in crisis and those who could use additional supports. In this model, clinicians listen to a student's story, empathise and validate, and connect them to appropriate supports. If an individual is in a crisis, we utilise the BeyondNow safety plan to work with students to support their safety and reduce their distress. If we are unable to reach a student or determine that they need additional support, we follow the university's specific procedures for wellbeing checks and further assistance. Each university has its own approach to managing risk [click here](#) to find the relevant guidelines for your institution.

Our team is guided by strict confidentiality agreements which work to enable students to discuss their experiences openly and honestly without concern or fear. Students are protected by these confidentiality agreements and this, in turn, supports their dignity.

COMPAS's attitude of respect extends to its team members, with clinicians working in pairs to enable a supportive network. Moreover, education on self-care and supervision occurs to support the wellbeing of the clinicians which, in turn, supports the wellbeing of students. The COMPAS team strives to maintain a warm and supportive working environment. We encourage feedback from all team members on how to improve the program wherever possible.

The COMPAS Model

Important Considerations

Everyone will have unique experiences, thoughts, behaviours, and attitudes regarding suicide. However, it is important that these do not hinder the interaction between the caller and the student. As such, it is important to leave personal judgements outside of these interactions and instead adopt an attitude of empathy and respect.

Active listening

Active listening should be employed throughout the conversation to help the individual feel heard and understood. If the individual feels valued and understood, they are more likely to be more engaged and participate actively in this interaction.

Collaboration

Each person's needs will vary considerably. The most effective interventions are those tailored to an individual's needs which can be addressed through collaborative problem-solving.

Collaborative problem-solving involves:

1. *Asking about the problem,*
2. *Forming a plan of action together, and*
3. *Offering referrals and available resources.*

Remember, the individual is an expert in their own experience. Use their expertise to create a safety plan that will be beneficial to them.

Looking after yourself

It is important to be aware of your own internal experiences during these interactions and outside of the room. If you find yourself being triggered by the content or notice some early warning signs, you should take steps to look after yourself. This may include revisiting the section on self-care in this manual ([pp. 33-35](#)), re-watching the online self-care training ([Lesson 2](#)), and seeking supervision.

Program Overview

Baseline COMPAS survey sent to first-year students

Procedure for Contacting At-risk Students

As per our Values Statement, the primary focus of every interaction with a student should be on their wellbeing, and their current needs as they understand them. We expect all clinical students to act with empathy, respect, and a person-centred approach to supporting students

All students who choose to take part in the COMPAS survey are told in the information sheet ([Appendix A](#)), that if their responses indicate they have been having a hard time or have experienced a series of negative events in the last 12 months, we will use the contact details they provide to touch base and offer some support.

At the end of the survey, students flagged as at-risk are informed:

“You indicated that at some time in the last 12 months you have been having a hard time or have experienced a series of negative events. We would like to quickly touch base with you to see how you are feeling and offer some support if we can. We’d also be interested in hearing about any support you have received in the last 12 months. We will use the phone number you provided to text you at some point in the next day or two, and arrange a time to have a chat.”

The Project Manager is alerted when a student is flagged as high risk (i.e., reported a suicide attempt in the last 12 months or identified by the algorithm). The student’s name, phone number, email address (for sending resources pdf), and age will be uploaded to a *Customer Relationship Management* (CRM) website, securely stored for you to access. The CRM will allow you to text or call the student directly from your computer while in the clinic. All relevant details are securely stored within the CRM, in accordance with local ethical data storage requirements.

Within the CRM, you will be able to see:

1. Contact details for all students assigned for you to contact,
2. Direct access to SMS and phone-calling options via the website,
3. The student’s preference to communicate over the phone or via SMS,
4. SMS templates for your initial contact, offering a suitable time to connect, statement of confidentiality, and more,
5. The date tasks are due for completion, such as when to contact the student by initially, and when to commence later follow-up communications, and
6. All required paperwork and clinical note-taking forms, with step-by-step lines for .

Before calling a student, check if phone communication is suitable.

Clinicians are to come into a designated confidential area in order to make contact with assigned students. A buddy system will be employed, where two clinicians will be in each area in case of a high or imminent suicide risk, allowing the second student to contact the appropriate services. Where possible, plan to make contact in blocks to optimise time spent at the designated area and with at least one other student.

Remember to set yourself shift times within your schedule, communicate these blocks of availability to your contact when relevant, and honour your other commitments. COMPAS is not a counselling service, and it's ok to tell students you will finish the conversation another day if you aren't able to get to the BeyondNow planning in time.

Unresponsive Contacts

Initiate contact with the student up to three times, over three different days. Through the CRM, you can SMS or call students directly via your desktop. **Never use your personal device, personal email, or a phone to contact students.** Your initial contact will let them know the days you are available to respond by text, or you will let them know over the phone or by voicemail if they are unavailable to talk for long when you first contact.

When texting students, you may sometimes have to refresh the browser before you can see their response. For students who prefer SMS, you may therefore want to plan to contact several in a block or have some other work available that can be dropped easily. When you are calling out, students will see the same phone number they see for incoming SMS messages, but all incoming phone calls from students will go directly to voicemail with the following recording:

"Thank you for calling COMPAS. Please note that this phone is not actively monitored, but your call will be recorded, and we will get back to you as soon as possible. If you are in distress or need immediate support, please contact Lifeline on 13 11 14 or, in an emergency, call 000. Thank you."

Students may respond at times when you are unavailable. The CRM will alert you if any of your assigned contacts have left a voicemail. You can call the student back or SMS to arrange a time for a longer call. Review voicemails and check for any SMS messages manually at the start of each shift, and take appropriate action.

If a student does not respond after three shifts where you have reached out:

1. Wait until near the end of your shift on the day of the third attempt (or the start of your next shift if you are responding to COMPAS messages the following day).
2. Text **and** email the "unresponsive template" [[also available here](#)] **in the CRM.**
3. Update the CRM form with as much detail as possible if voicemails were left.
4. Note in the CRM you have attempted to contact the student 3 times without reply.
5. Close the task in the CRM and delete the 4-week follow-up task.
6. Tag the contact as unresponsive and inform the Project Manager.

The templates you send will inform the student they may be contacted by campus security to check on their immediate wellbeing, and include a list of available support resources [[which can also be found here](#)]. **You will not conduct a 4-week follow-up.**

Opting Out

If at any point a student communicates they do not want to be contacted, please send the templates for "opting out" (to re-send the list of resources via text and email and inform them that the team will not contact them further).

Note in the CRM when the contact occurred, finalise any form details you can, and close the "Initial contact" and "Follow-up" tasks. If the student needs more urgent crisis care, then please prioritise this in the call log. **You will not conduct a 4-week follow-up.**

Contact Assessment Flowchart

Phone Call Scripts

Each interaction with a student will be unique, as no two students will share the same experience or have the same needs. These scripts are intended as a guide to help you talk with students.

A: Opening Script Initial Contact

Refer to the CRM flowchart ([Appendix D](#)) for guidance on all student communications. The flowchart outlines the steps for completing the contact checklist accurately and efficiently.

When initiating a student call, use the following script:

Hi [insert student name], I'm [insert your name] from COMPAS. Can I just confirm that I'm speaking with [confirm student's name]?

If not: *"No worries, I will call back later. Thank you."*
Do not disclose what this call is about.

If yes: *"I'm following up on the COMPAS wellbeing survey you recently completed. Are you free to talk at the moment?"*

If student responds NO:	If a student does not answer the phone:
<p><i>"No worries, I just wanted to touch base with you about your responses on the survey. It sounds like you've been through a difficult time, so I'm just calling to see if you are receiving any support or if there is any support we can offer. Would it be ok for me to arrange a time for me to phone you back when you can chat?"</i> [arrange a time to call them back]</p>	<p>Leave a voicemail message: <i>"It's [your name] from COMPAS. Sorry I've missed you. I'll try calling again tomorrow."</i></p> <p>Second phone call - if not answered, leave another voicemail message: <i>"It's [insert your name] from COMPAS. Sorry I've missed you again. I'll call again tomorrow for one last time. I hope to speak to you then."</i></p> <p>Third phone call not answered: <i>"It's [your name] from COMPAS. Sorry I missed you again. Our team follows everyone up 4 weeks after taking the survey, so I'll get back in touch in 4 weeks' time. In the meantime, I'll email you some resources you might find useful. Thanks again for doing the survey."</i></p>

If YES, continue:

"Thanks [student first name], my role in the team is to follow up with students who have completed the online survey and whose responses indicate they may benefit from some mental health support. It sounds like you've been through a difficult time, so I'm calling to check in on how you're going at the moment and to offer information and support if you think it would be helpful for you.

I'm not a counsellor, but my role is to help connect you with support services if you feel that would be useful. I have set aside 50 minutes for a chat about how we might be able to support you at uni.

Also, I just wanted to let you know that everything we talk about is confidential—it stays between you, me, and my team. However, there are some special circumstances where I may have to break confidentiality, such as if you tell me you might be at risk of harm to yourself or someone else, or if my records are requested by the courts. If any of these situations arise, I will discuss them with you first."

If the situation is complex and requires more than 50 minutes, then re-establish expectations around the call (e.g., *"I am happy to stay on the line with you and continue to support you, but I need to let you know that I have to leave the office at 5pm. Would it be ok if I check in with you again tomorrow"*). Alternatively, recommend the student contact another service (e.g., Lifeline) who is available. (e.g., *"I'm afraid I will need to leave this call in 15 minutes. How would you feel about calling Lifeline to continue getting support today?"*)

Firstly, try to establish some rapport and put them at ease.

Allow students to tell you their story and how they are feeling. Don't jump to conclusions about what is going on for them or what their needs are. *The majority of students will not be suicidal when you call, but may like support in other areas (e.g., adapting to university pressures, making new friends at university).*

Once some rapport is established, **ask directly if they have been considering suicide.**

It is important to wait until rapport has been sufficiently built before asking about suicide. If asked too early in the phone call, rapport can be ruptured and may affect an individual's willingness to disclose.

Other useful questions to assist about asking for suicide may include:

- Have you had any thoughts of suicide recently?
- You mentioned that you have been/are feeling [x]. Are you thinking about suicide?
- Sometimes when people feel it can lead to thoughts of suicide. Is that happening to you?
- Have you ever wanted to end your life? / Have you thought about ending your life?
- You are going through so much. Have you wanted to escape from your life?

Update the CRM after any contact or attempts

If YES, respond:

Provide an empathic response to their disclosure. Some useful reflections may include:

"I'm sorry to hear that things are difficult for you at the moment." (Provide empathic response) "It sounds like everything is so _____ (e.g., overwhelming) that you feel suicide is your only choice..."

"Thank you for telling me that, I know it can be hard letting people know what is going on."

Take a breath. It can be difficult to ask about suicide, and upsetting to hear that an individual is experiencing suicidal thoughts and/or behaviours. It can be helpful to explicitly name this (e.g., "Okay, so we're talking about suicide").

Conduct suicide risk assessment using the COMPAS model to lead to safety planning. Establish the level of risk by listening and asking if they have a suicide plan.

Listen: Listen to students' stories and listen for indicators of distress or invitations about suicide.

Explore and empathise: Explore their situation, inc. if they have plans, means, etc.

Safety plans and supports: Work collaboratively with the student to identify what supports they have and work to develop a safety plan.

If Very High/Imminent Risk

(e.g., plan already partially enacted or intent to enact plan imminently and the person does not agree to safety planning)

Ask the person where they are located. Enquire if the student would be comfortable calling 000 (or local emergency services depending on location). If not, ask for their permission to contact other services, including emergency services (police, ambulance, etc.). **Note:** No call should be made without the student's permission unless they are at immediate risk of harm to themselves or others, in accordance with the APS Code of Ethics and confidentiality (addressed at the start of the call).

Try to keep the student on the phone while you contact 000. Continue liaising with the student and emergency services (such as campus security or relevant support services if available) until care is handed over to emergency services, healthcare providers, or a family member/friend/partner who agrees to escort the student to the hospital emergency department for assessment.

Information about emergency departments, including estimated wait times, is linked on [pg. 29](#) and will be available in the CRM.

Contact the delegated supervisor to review and debrief. Update case notes in the CRM.

Three days later, send a text message asking about the helpfulness of the call ([TEXT MESSAGE 3](#)). Record the student's response or lack of response in the CRM. (Use your judgement as to whether a follow-up text is appropriate given the individual student's circumstances).

Follow-up in 4 weeks as per usual procedure (**note:** a follow-up within 24 hours may be appropriate depending on the outcome of the call)

If Moderate to High Risk
(e.g., they have a suicide plan but no intent)

Find out more about their plan (i.e., when were they thinking of doing this and how). Use the COMPAS model to connect with student (ask about thoughts of suicide), understand choices (hear the story, listen for reasons living), and assist life (develop a safety plan and confirm actions).

Use **BeyondNow** to guide the safety plan including what current supports they have, and how/when they can use them. Ask the student to download the BeyondNow app to their phone so you can work with them to complete this in tandem (see if the student has a headset and can ensure their privacy as this is done). Work through each step of the plan with the student, and remind them they can make changes to their plan on their phone at any time. Document the safety plan by saving the version you have written simultaneously so it can be emailed to them if asked.

As part of the plan discuss the option of seeing their GP or the university GP. Provide the Lifeline crisis number within the plan (13 11 14). Explain that the GP can organise an appropriate referral for ongoing support (i.e., a Mental Healthcare Plan). If the student decides to see a GP for a Mental Healthcare Plan, outline what this process involves. Discuss the kind of support that is available in the community, including GPs, Men's Talk, Recovery Matters, psychologists, headspace centres, and crisis phone lines. See [COMPAS National resources](#).

Contact the delegated supervisor to review and debrief.

Three days later, sent a text message asking about the helpfulness of the call ([TEXT MESSAGE 3](#)). Record the student's response in the CRM (Use your judgement as to whether a follow-up text is appropriate given the individual student's circumstances.)

Follow up in 4 weeks.

If Low Risk
(e.g., some thoughts of suicide but no plan or intent,
or no suicidal thoughts/behaviours)

Explore how they have been feeling, and encourage them to talk about it with you. Ask them what strategies they have been using to feel better.

Ask whether they would be interested in hearing about some resources/support that might be useful. If they are interested, talk further with them about the services that might be appropriate and then send them some specific information. Link them to the list of available resources nationally or at their local university through the [COMPAS website](#) if they do not express specific needs and prefer to browse.

Three days later, sent a text message asking about the helpfulness of the call ([TEXT MESSAGE 3](#)). Record the student's response in the CRM. (Use your own judgement as to whether follow-up text is appropriate given the individual student's circumstances.)

Follow-up in 4 weeks.

If No

(i.e., they respond they have not felt any suicidal thoughts recently)

Take a breath. Remain calm and non-judgemental (i.e., don't respond with "That's great!").

Do respond: *"So it sounds like you've been doing your best to cope with things at the moment. What has helped or what has changed for you?"* (if historic experiences of suicidal thoughts and behaviours).

"I'm interested to hear about what you do to cope with stress. What else helps to keep you well?" [allow a person to speak about strategies, pay attention to any comments that suggest the person is not doing well]

"Who have you got for ongoing support?" (Prompt: counsellor, friends, family, romantic partner(s), other)

If they are accessing informal support, encourage the student to continue to access the support: *"Fantastic. It's really important to have a good support network."*

If not accessing informal support, gently explore this as an option: *"Sometimes it can be really helpful to grab a coffee and chat with a friend or someone you trust."*

If they do not indicate any formal support (e.g., a therapist), ask them if they think this might be useful and if so, provide some referral information appropriate to the level of need: *"When you've gone through difficult times in the past, have you considered getting some help from a therapist/counsellor?"*

If a student has accessed a counsellor: *"Would you be willing to see that person again if you were going through a tough time in the future?"*

If a student has not accessed support services: *"Do you think it would be helpful to have some contact details of other people who can help?"* [If yes, offer to provide these details again – email written material.]

Explore this with them if they seem interested but don't push.

To conclude call:

"Thanks for chatting with me today. We are contacting everyone again after 4 weeks, so would it be ok for me to call back then to see how you're going?" [If yes, try and ascertain the best days/times]

Three days later:

Send the following text message.

*Hi [student]. Thank you for taking our call. We would appreciate some feedback. How helpful did you find our discussion the other day from 1) unhelpful, 2) neither, or 3) helpful? Thank you.
Kind regards, COMPAS team"*

Record response in CRM.

B: BeyondNow: Guide for Safety Planning

The goal of safety planning is for people to become more aware of their personal warning signs that a suicidal crisis is beginning or escalating so they can take action to keep safe before they are in danger of acting on their suicidal feelings, and to provide them with a plan they can follow in times when their distress has escalated (Stanley & Brown, 2017; 2021).

Encourage the student to download the BeyondNow app so they can complete it on their own phone as you work through it with them on your device. Links to the BeyondNow app (for download with Apple App Store or Google Play) or webpage can be accessed via the Lifeline website.

Direct link to download the BeyondNow App at Apple App Store: [click here](#)

Direct link to download the BeyondNow App at Google Play: [click here](#)

Direct link to the BeyondNow webpage: [click here](#)

The BeyondNow Safety Plan has 7 steps that are summarised below beside screenshots of how each section appears when using the BeyondNow webpage. **Note.** The app may have these steps in a different order. If the student is using the app version, it may be best to use this too, on your own phone. Work through each step in the way that best supports the student.

1. My Warning Signs

One of the most effective ways of averting a suicidal crisis is to address difficulties before they fully escalate. The first step of a safety plan involves identifying the warning signs that immediately precede a suicidal crisis. Being aware of changes in thoughts, moods, and behaviour that may signal a developing crisis allows the person to act earlier, helping reduce further risk.

Questions to ask might include:

How will you know when your safety plan should be used?

What are some of the difficult thoughts, feelings, or behaviours that you experience leading up to a crisis?

Warning signs might include:

Moods such as sadness, anxiety, irritability...

Thoughts involving hopelessness, helplessness, or self-criticism etc.

Behaviours such as drinking more alcohol than usual, avoiding social situations, or arguing more often with friends or loved ones, etc.

STEP 1 OF 7

My warning signs

Warning signs are changes that let you know you're heading into a crisis. Knowing your warning signs can help you act early. What are your warning signs?

My warning signs are...

Add

Suggestions

You can click/tap to add as one of yours. You can select more than one

- + I feel hopeless
- + Sleeping is hard
- + I don't want to talk to anyone
- + I feel like a burden
- + I'm struggling to keep up with my normal routine
- + I'm fighting with people
- + I feel like I don't belong, or I won't be accepted

Keep going →

2. Creating a Safe Environment

The next step involves identifying ways of keeping the person's immediate environment safe by reducing or eliminating their access to potentially lethal means. This step can also include being aware of and avoiding stressful or upsetting situations.

Questions to ask might include:

Are there any specific situations or people that you find stressful or triggering, or that contribute to your suicidal thoughts?

What things do you have access to that are likely to be used in a suicide attempt?

How can we develop a plan to limit your access to these means and keep you safe?

Restricting access to lethal means might include:

Asking someone else to manage access to medication

Reducing access to means or improving safety procedures

Getting rid of glass or blades that might be used to cause harm

3. My Reasons to Live

Experiencing suicidal ideation is often mentally consuming, and it can be hard to see the positive things in life that bring joy and meaning. The next step of a safety plan involves having a pre-written list of reasons to live. These help the person remember things they enjoy or can look forward to.

Questions to ask might include:

What's the best thing about living?

What's the most important thing in your life?

What things in your future do you look forward to?

Reasons to live might include:

Family, friends, or pets

Spiritual or religious beliefs

Everyday pleasures such as walking on the beach or enjoying nature

Life experiences such as having children or travelling

STEP 2 OF 7

Make my space safe

It's important to make your space as safe as you can. Get rid of stuff that could be used to end your life.

Things I can do...

Add

Suggestions

You can click/tap to add as one of yours. You can select more than one

+ Give my medication to someone else to look after

+ Lock up or get rid of anything I could use to harm myself

+ Give my car keys to someone to look after

← Previous

Keep going →

STEP 3 OF 7

My reasons to live

When you're feeling suicidal, it's easy to forget about the good things in life. Thinking about these things can help you manage until the feelings pass. Write down things that make you want to live - big or small!

My reasons to live are...

Add

Suggestions

You can click/tap to add as one of yours. You can select more than one

+ Things I haven't done yet

+ Helping others, like my mob

+ Seeing my kids grow up

+ My pet

+ My best mate

← Previous

Keep going →

4. Things I Can Do By Myself

Suicidal thoughts can make it hard to focus on anything else. Activities and internal coping strategies help the person distract themselves from suicidal ideation, potentially preventing a further escalation into crisis. Identifying internal strategies as a first-line response improves the person's ability and self-confidence in managing warning signs or suicidal thoughts.

Questions to ask might include:

What can you do on your own if you have suicidal thoughts in the future, to avoid acting on those thoughts?

What can you do to help take your mind off your problems, even for a short amount of time?

Internal coping strategies might include:

Breathing or relaxation exercises

Going for a walk, doing yoga, or other exercise

Watching a favourite movie or listening to a favourite band

Playing or cuddling with a pet

5. Connect with People and Places

If the person isn't able to reduce their distress or suicidal ideation using internal coping strategies, the next step is to try some passive socialisation strategies. Just being around other people can help provide distraction from suicidal thoughts – this can include spending time with family and friends or going to a busy park or shopping centre. This step is really about spending time in a social setting, rather than reaching out and discussing their thoughts and feelings – that comes next. You should also remind the student about avoiding social environments where alcohol or other drugs might be involved.

Questions to ask might include:

Who helps you to feel good when you hang out with them?

Where can you go and be around other people in a safe environment?

Socialisation strategies might include:

Spending time with friends and family, remembering that socialising can include activities that don't require much talking or engagement, such as watching TV.

A coffee shop, park, place of worship, or meeting group

STEP 4 OF 7

Things I can do by myself

Doing things to distract yourself from suicidal thoughts can help keep you safe. List some of the things you like doing by yourself.

Things I can do...

 Add

Suggestions

You can click/tap to add as one of yours. You can select more than one

- + Listen to music
- + Take a shower or bath
- + Walk outside
- + Watch something (a film/YouTube clip/TV)
- + Do some exercise
- + Write something
- + Practice relaxation techniques

← Previous

Keep going →

STEP 5 OF 7

People and places I can connect with

Just being around other people can make you feel better. Make a list of people you could spend time with or places you can go to be around other people.

My people and places...

 Add

Suggestions

You can click/tap to add as one of yours. You can select more than one

- + Go to a park or visit country
- + Invite a friend over to watch a movie
- + Exercise at the gym
- + Spend some time in a café
- + Hang out at the library
- + Go somewhere I feel accepted
- + Connect to my culture

← Previous

Keep going →

6. Friends and Family I can talk to

If the person is still in crisis after working through their internal coping and socialisation strategies, the next step in their plan involves sharing their thoughts and feelings with a trusted friend or family member. This differs from the previous step in that people are encouraged to explicitly reveal that they're struggling with suicidal ideation and need support in coping with the crisis. For this step, the person should think carefully about who would be helpful in a crisis and avoid listing people who could possibly exacerbate the situation.

Questions to ask might include:

Among your friends and family, who do you feel you could talk to when you're having suicidal thoughts?

Who do you feel you could contact to support you during a suicidal crisis?

STEP 6 OF 7

People I can talk or yarn to

People you trust can help you stay safe and feel better. List the people you can talk or yarn to when you feel suicidal.

People I can talk to...

Name
Phone
Only use numbers and spaces.
Alt. contact (phone, email, etc)
Add

← Previous

Keep going →

7. Professional Contacts

The final step involves listing professional support services the person can contact when they need to.

Questions to ask might include:

Which services could you turn to for support?

(If the student is struggling, can refer to [List of Resources](#), for ideas)

STEP 7 OF 7

Professional support

Professional support is always there if you need it. List the services that work for you. **In an emergency, always call 000.**

- 000
- Suicide Call Back Service 1300 659467 (24/7)
- Lifeline 13 11 14 (24/7)

My contacts...

Name
Phone
Only use numbers and spaces.
Alt. contact (phone, email, etc)
Add

← Previous

Keep going →

C: Four-Week Follow-Up

When the CRM indicates that a 4-week follow-up is due, send the “4-week follow-up” SMS template. If phone calls have been used previously, or if the student prefers a phone call, use the following message to let them know they can expect a call:

SMS Template:

“Dear [STUDENT FIRST NAME], it’s [YOUR NAME] from COMPAS. When we last spoke, I mentioned that we follow up with everyone after around 4 weeks to check in and see how you’re doing. I’ll be reaching out to you via [your preferred contact method—SMS or phone call] within the next 24 hours. Thank you for taking the time to respond.”

First Attempt:

- Send an SMS or make a phone call, depending on the student's preference
- If no response is received, proceed with the second attempt using the pre-populated template and follow-up communication process.

Second Attempt:

- If there’s no response after the first attempt, send a second SMS or make a phone call.
- You can use the same script or modify the message to encourage them to engage, depending on your communication style and history with the student.

Third Attempt:

- If no response has been received after two previous attempts on separate shifts, send a third SMS or make a phone call.
- If there is still no reply, close the task in the CRM, add the “Unresponsive Contact” tag, and follow the same [Unresponsive Contact](#) protocol as for the initial contact.

Here’s a suggested message:

- Phone Call Script: *“Hi [Student’s Name], it’s [Your Name] from COMPAS. I’ve tried reaching you a couple of times, and as we haven’t been able to connect, we’ll be closing your contact for now. However, we will follow up with you again in one year to check in. If you’d like to discuss anything in the meantime, please feel free to get in touch. Thanks for your time.”*

For SMS-based contacts, send the Unresponsive Contact template.

Please make sure that *all attempts to contact the student are logged in the CRM*, and that you indicate this as the final step in their follow-up process. Do not wait for a task to finish before updating form fields or your case notes in the CRM.

Follow-up Conversation (Once Contact is Made):

- If the student responds at any stage, re-establish rapport: *“Hi [STUDENT NAME], it’s [YOUR NAME] from COMPAS. Thanks for speaking with me again.”*

Personalise the conversation based on prior interactions, such as:

- **If support services were discussed previously:** *“I’m following up to see how you’re doing and whether you’ve accessed any support services since we last spoke. How have you been?”*
- **If the student mentioned a specific service:** *“I’m following up to check in and see if you had any luck seeing [INSERT SERVICE] since we last spoke?”*
- **If no services were discussed:** *“I’m just following up to check in and ask how things have been since we last spoke.”*

If there is a need to update the safety plan, ask the following questions and record their responses in real-time within the CRM.

Safety Plan Update Questions:

- How are you managing academically?
- Are you finding the workload manageable, or would you like additional academic support?

Ending four-week follow-up (for no/low risk students)

"Thank you for speaking with me today. Is there anything else you'd like to mention to me about what we've discussed?"

Would you find it helpful if I re-sent you the list of services?

Before we end the conversation, could I please ask you a couple of final questions?

[If yes:]

1. *Since we last spoke, how have your problems changed?
(0) Worse, (1) No change, (2) Better.*
2. *Since the last call, how would you rate your ability to cope with life in general? (0) Much worse, (1) No change, (2) Better, (3) Much better, (4) Very much better*
3. *How acceptable have you found the communication from the COMPAS team? (0) Not at all acceptable, (1) Acceptable, (2) Very acceptable, (3) Extremely acceptable*
4. *How important do you feel follow-up calls from the COMPAS team are for students who may be highly distressed? (0) Not important, (1) Moderately important, (2) Very important, (3) Extremely important*
5. *Overall, how helpful have you found our discussions, whether by phone or text, both during the initial call and today? (0) Unhelpful, (1) Helpful, (2) Neither helpful nor unhelpful"*

!!! You can find more text templates in the CRM's ClickSend modules and [Appendix C](#) !!!

D: One-Year Follow-Up

One-year follow-ups will be conducted for students who were identified as high risk for future suicide behaviour when they previously did the baseline survey. The procedure will be the same as for the 4-week follow-ups, except that you will not be familiar with the student and will ask about the past year, rather than the past 4 weeks.

Text the student with one of the following messages:

TEXT MESSAGE 4a [For days you are in the clinic and will be again tomorrow] -

*“Dear [insert student name],
It’s [insert your name] from COMPAS. You did the COMPAS survey about 1 year ago. We like to follow up after a year to see how people are going and, if relevant, offer some support for times when you think it might be helpful. I will give you a call in the next 24 hours. Thanks for taking the call.”*

TEXT MESSAGE 4b [Indicating that you will contact them on your next available day]:

“Dear [student name], it’s [your name] from COMPAS. You did the survey about 1 year ago. We like to follow up after a year to see how people are going and, if relevant, offer some support for times when you think it might be helpful. A member of the COMPAS team will call you on [Next available shift]. Thanks for taking the call.”

Open the student’s account on the CRM ahead of the call so you can enter their responses during the conversation and be prompted for the talking points.

Conduct the follow-up conversation:

Opening script for calls

“Hi [student name], I’m [your name] from COMPAS. Can I just confirm that I’m speaking with [student’s name]? I’m following up on the COMPAS Survey you completed last year. Are you free to talk at the moment?”

If student responds NO:	If student does not answer the phone:
<p><i>“No worries, I just wanted to touch base with you about your responses on the survey. We are following up everyone who had a pattern of responses that indicated they may have experienced a difficult time, and might be at higher risk for suicidal thoughts or behaviours in the future. It sounded like you went through a difficult time in the past, so I’m just calling to see how the past 12 months have been for you – if you are receiving any support or if there is any support we can offer. Would it be ok for me to arrange a time for me to call you back?”</i></p> <p>[arrange a time to call them back]</p>	<p>Leave a voicemail message: <i>“It’s [your name] from COMPAS. Sorry, I’ve missed you. I’ll try and call you back tomorrow.”</i></p> <p>Second phone call: if not answered, leave another voicemail message: <i>“It’s [your name] from COMPAS. Sorry, I’ve missed you again. I’ll call again tomorrow for one last time. I hope to speak to you then.”</i></p> <p>Third phone call not answered: <i>“It’s [insert your name] from COMPAS. Sorry, I missed you again. I’ll email you some resources you might find useful. Thanks again for doing the survey.”</i></p>

If YES, continue:

"Thanks [student name], my role in the team is to follow up with students who completed the online survey and who had a pattern of responses that indicated they may have experienced a difficult time and might be at higher risk for suicidal thoughts or behaviours in the future. It sounded like you went through a difficult time in the past, so I'm just calling to see how the past 12 months have been for you – if you are receiving any support already, or to offer information and support if you think it would be helpful for you. I'm not a counsellor, but my role is to help link you in with some support services if you feel that would be useful.

So how are things going for you at the moment?"

If indicated, conduct another risk assessment and follow risk procedures. If risk is low, then proceed with asking the follow-up survey questions:

Enter responses in real-time as you speak to them.

The aim here is to establish some rapport, put them at ease and let them tell you generally how they are feeling

Ending the one-year follow-up (for no/low risk students)

"Thank you for speaking with me today. Is there anything else you would like to mention about what we've talked about? Would it be helpful for me to re-send you the list of services?"

Before we end the call, can I please just ask you a couple of final questions?

[If yes:]

Since you received the first call after the survey (1 year ago), your problem(s) have become: (0) worse, (1) not changed, (2) better.

Since you received the first call after the survey (1 year ago), your ability to cope with life in general has become: (0) much worse, (1) no change, (2) better, (3) much better, (4) very much better.

You have found the phone calls from the COMPAS team to be: (0) not at all acceptable, (1) acceptable, (2) very acceptable, (4) extremely acceptable.

How important do you feel it is that the follow-up calls from the COMPAS team be made available to students who may be highly distressed? (0) no importance, (1) moderately important, (2) very important, (3) extremely important.

Overall, how helpful have you found our discussions on the phone? Unhelpful, Helpful, or Neither.

Ok, thanks again for taking my call. All students will be invited to complete the questionnaire again at the beginning of next year, and we do yearly phone follow-ups like this whilst people are at university, but we won't contact you again this year. All the best for your studies this year."

Make this a conversation, rather than a survey.
Remember to validate how the person has been feeling.
Check in with:
• How helpful services and resources were to them.
• How they dealt with those feelings.
• Did they have a safety plan? Did they follow it?
• Do they want to update it now?
Do all this before asking about service use.

E: Email provision of resources following calls

Following the phone call, provide the student with a copy of the resources discussed on the call. The clinical team member will email the student from within the CRM. Templates to use and how to find email modules in the CRM is in [Appendix C](#).

Resources list: <https://www.compas.org.au/resources>

Training

All clinical students will undergo an online training program wherein these models, procedures, and concepts are explained in more detail.

Students will then attend a one-day in-person session with an opportunity to engage in roleplays with various levels of risk and practise using the telehealth systems.

Daily Operating Procedures

At the start of each shift, clinical students must complete the following duties:

- Check for new assigned tasks
- Check for any missed calls and unread texts – you must review all notifications in the CRM
- Action and Document – Determine the appropriate course of action for each and ensure detailed documentation in the CRM
- Finalise any unresponsive contacts ([pg. 13](#))
- Arrange any follow-up contacts

Level of Risk

The idea of stratifying individuals into levels of high or low risk is a contentious one.

While some people find it useful to have a guide to help determine the next steps, the reality is such classifications do not reliably predict suicidal behaviour. Further, risk assessments that are based on assessment of prior suicidal behaviour and mental illness are less than 5% accurate in identifying future suicidal behaviour. Instead, researchers and clinicians are arguing for multivariable psychosocial assessments rather than risk assessments. In addition, there is growing recognition that adopting a person-centred, rather than medical, view of suicidal thoughts and behaviours is a more compassionate, personalised, and humane way of working with people experiencing suicidal thoughts and/or behaviours.

This is the essence of COMPAS – to provide a comprehensive psychosocial assessment, and person-centred follow-up assessing each student's needs at that particular time.

In 2022, the National Institute for Health and Care Excellence (NICE) updated its guidelines for assessment, management, and preventing recurrence of self-harm (broadly defined). Members of the guideline committee (Mughal et al., 2023) highlight their care recommendations as follows:

- The need for empathy
- No aversive treatments
- Psychosocial assessment, not risk assessment
- Compassionate and person-centred care

The **Integrated Motivational-Volition Model of Suicidal Behaviour** (O'Connor & Kirtley, 2018) provides some indication of factors that may elevate the risk of suicidal behaviour. These include background factors, intra and interpersonal factors (coping skills, rumination), motivational factors (e.g. goals, thwarted belongingness, reasons for living), and volitional factors (e.g., access to means, fearlessness about suicide). Please read the paper at the back of this training manual for a detailed description of the model.

Hospital emergency services

You can find the current estimated wait times for metropolitan emergency departments at:

New South Wales: <https://www.emergencywait.health.nsw.gov.au/>

Northern Territory: <https://nt.gov.au>

Queensland: <https://openhospitals.health.qld.gov.au/>

South Australia: <https://www.sahealth.sa.gov.au>

Victoria: <https://vahi.vic.gov.au>

Western Australia: <https://ww2.health.wa.gov.au>

Country Services

Country hospitals and nursing posts provide or can arrange emergency services [[linked on the National Resources page](#)]. Ambulance services or the **Royal Flying Doctor Service** can also help you access emergency services.

Email Templates

A generic email (COMPAS-S@curtin.edu.au) has been set up to allow streamlined contact between the COMPAS team and students. This should only be used to send students resources.

The following templates should be used.

If the student was agreeable and you are sending the discussed resources, the following template should be used:

Dear [student's first name],

Recently you chatted with [Clinical student's name], one of the COMPAS team members about your wellbeing and how you are feeling. Thanks for touching base with us.

Following up from the conversation, attached here is [what is being sent]. If you start to experience your warning signs, work through the steps until you feel safe. [OR] [insert information about services you are making available].

Thanks again and best wishes,

COMPAS Team

If the student has communicated that they want no contact, re-send the link to available resources. The following template should be used:

Dear [student's first name],

Thank you for completing the COMPAS survey. You have indicated that you do not wish to be contacted again, which we respect. I am linking a list of resources available to you, should you find them helpful: <https://www.compas.org.au/resourcespage>.

Thank you again and best wishes,

[insert your first name]

Text Messaging Procedures & Templates

Text messaging is the most common form of communication with students. However, when possible, transitioning to a conversation can be more effective for sharing information and providing better support. Honour the student's preferred contact method, especially in the first instance, but don't be afraid to be flexible, offer options, and adapt to the student's preferred communication style as often as they express a preference. Below are frequently used text templates for different scenarios.

TEXT MESSAGE 1a: Initial Contact (In clinic):

Hi %First_Name%, this is [YOUR NAME] from COMPAS. You recently completed a wellbeing survey, and we would like to check in to see how you are going. I am available for a chat at [Time Option 1] or [Time Option 2], but I'm happy to arrange another time that works better for you via your preferred contact method. Let me know what suits you! I can also give you a call at those times if you prefer a proper conversation about this. You can also find more information and resources here: <https://www.compas.org.au/resourcespage>.

TEXT MESSAGE 1b: Initial Contact (Out of clinic)

Hi %First_Name%, recently, you completed an online survey about your wellbeing. We'd like to check in and offer support for times when you might find it helpful. A COMPAS team member will be in touch on [NEXT SHIFT DAY]. Looking forward to connecting with you then.

TEXT MESSAGE 2: Transitioning from Text to a Conversation

I think it might be easier for us to talk through this and find the right support if we move to a conversation. Would you be okay with that? Let me know what works best for you.

To help set expectations, gently introduce the idea of a conversation as early as possible. Let the student know they can continue by text if needed, but a more direct discussion may be helpful.

TEXT MESSAGE 3: Feedback on Helpfulness of Conversation

Hi %First_Name%, thank you for taking the time to connect. We'd appreciate some quick feedback. How helpful did you find our discussion today?

1. Unhelpful
2. Neither helpful nor unhelpful
3. Helpful

Thank you. Kind regards, COMPAS Team

Documentation of Contact Attempts

Accurate record-keeping is vital to ensure the team stays informed, to support other clinicians in case you are unwell, to inform the clinician completing the one-year follow-up, and to ensure that all decisions are documented and justified. Completing the call record in the CRM is essential for maintaining consistency, tracking student interactions, and ensuring proper documentation for every contact attempt.

All student contacts and attempts at contacting students must be recorded in the CRM, which serves as the central system for monitoring outreach efforts and maintaining continuity of care. Every contact attempt must be documented, even if there is no response.

CRM Documentation Process

For each contact attempt, complete the call record in the CRM.

- If the initial contact is completed but the student does not respond, close the task and create a new task using the pre-populated 'Second Contact' title.
- If there is no response to the second contact attempt, complete the contact record as much as possible, make a note at the bottom, then close the task and create a new task using the pre-populated 'Third Contact' title.
- If there is still no response after the third attempt, use the '**Unresponsive Contact**' tag and escalate the case to the Project Manager to action further.

Additionally, you may find it helpful to record de-identified follow-ups in your personal calendar as reminders for upcoming check-ins.

([Appendix B](#) shows the documentation required in the CRM)

Call Record Sheet

All documentation should clearly detail the following:

- Time and date of the contact attempt
- Purpose of the contact (e.g., initial attempt, confirming a resource name after researching, etc)
- The outcome of the attempt, regardless of whether you receive a response
- The attempt number
- (If relevant) The length of the call
- Next planned course of action (e.g., close task and contact at follow-up, email resources, etc.)

All notes should be signed off with the student’s name, title (e.g., clinical psychologist trainee), date (in format DD MM YYYY) and signed.

If contact is not made:	If contact is made:
<p>Detail attempt number this is, and if a voicemail was left, or the nature of the SMS.</p>	<p>Determine if agreeable to talk now.</p>
	<p>If NOT agreeable to talk now, detail:</p>
	<p>That the student was not agreeable to a callback and the time of the interaction.</p>
	<p>If AGREEABLE to talk now, detail the:</p>
	<p>The date. Whether a risk assessment was completed and the determined risk level. If a safety plan was completed, and if so, resources and coping strategies were identified by the student.</p> <p>If a student is identified to be a ‘high’ or ‘very high/imminent’ risk, then master’s students are required to debrief with allocated clinical supervisors. The date, time, and supervisor consulted must be detailed in the CRM notes.</p>

Call Monitoring Form

Similarly, all calls should be documented on the CRM (this will be covered in the online training and in-person training):

Self-Care

Being present and connecting to individuals who are struggling may affect your wellbeing. These interactions can have a compounding effect with the more calls you take. Consequently, it is important to be aware of this impact on you and to take steps to look after yourself. Some warning signs that these calls may be affecting you may include:

- Getting sick more often
- Feeling low or irritable
- Having no motivation or energy
- Feeling overwhelmed or hopeless
- Difficulty falling and/or staying asleep
- Increased headaches, stomach aches, or other physical symptoms of stress
- Worsening mental health symptoms.

Awareness

You need to know your personal warning signs so if these arise, you can address them. You should engage in self-reflection regularly and be honest about the impact of stressors on your wellbeing. Tools and strategies to develop awareness:

- Mindfulness and meditation training
- Engagement in reflective practice
- Discussion of difficult calls
- Consultation with supervisors and peer

Note. This is not an exhaustive list, but rather a few signs and symptoms to look for.

If you notice yourself displaying these warning signs, it may indicate that you need to seek supervision and engage in more self-care. Self-care refers to a clinical and ethical imperative of looking after yourself to maintain your psychological, emotional, and physiological wellbeing. There are a few components of self-care, alongside tools and strategies to support each component, which are explored below (Posluns & Gall, 2020).

Physical Health

Looking after your physical health is important as this is a protective factor in maintaining your wellbeing. Although these may be things, we all know, we may not do this or may be the first thing we stop when things get busy. Aim to:

- Maintain a regular sleep schedule
- Get the recommended 7-9 hours per night
- Regularly exercise
- Eat a balanced diet
- Get enough hydration daily

Prioritise Balance

Try to maintain a balance between your professional and personal demands. Some tools and strategies that may be beneficial include:

- Making leisure time a priority
- Cultivation of non-work related interests, hobbies, and relationships
- Maintenance of good work and personal boundaries
- Taking breaks
- Setting realistic work goals
- Use of time-management skills

Social Support

Engage with your social supports, but also utilise professional resources and connections available to you. This may include seeking:

- Professional supervision from clinical supervisors and/or mentors.
- Peer supervision.

Some things to consider before, during, and after these interactions are provided below (Evans, 2015).

Before interactions:

- Check in with how you are feeling and whether you are in a good space. If you are dealing with external pressures, try leaving them at the door of the clinic
- Practise some form of grounding, relaxation, or mindfulness practice

During interactions:

- If you are feeling overwhelmed, take some deep breaths or complete a grounding exercise
- Try to remain focused on the present

Between interactions:

- Take breaks when you need
- Make sure to look after your physical needs too, like staying hydrated, eating, and stretching

After interactions:

- Reflect on both the successful and challenging parts of the interaction
- Identify any emotional reactions you have or had (do not ignore or suppress these)
- If it was a particularly challenging interaction, arrange to debrief with either peers or your clinical supervisor

It is important to know that you may experience either compassion fatigue or vicarious trauma. **Compassion fatigue** refers to the emotional and physical erosion that occurs when an individual cannot refuel and regenerate. Anyone can experience compassion fatigue, and it does not require exposure to traumatic materials.

Vicarious trauma refers to the experience of distress that can result from exposure to other individuals' trauma. Vicarious trauma can have a substantial impact, including affecting the way you think, your worldview, your relationships, and your physical functioning. If identified early, symptoms can be managed effectively through appropriate support and engagement in self-care strategies. The experience varies among individuals, so it is important to understand how you "normally" function or your baseline experience. Some signs that you may be experiencing vicarious trauma:

- Disturbed sleep
- Frustration/anger/anxiety/irritability
- Invasive thoughts of the other individuals' situation or their distress
- Changes in your worldview or sense of safety
- Difficulty leaving work on time and/or leaving work at the end of the day
- Loss of connection to yourself and/or loved ones
- Loss of pleasure in daily activities/those that used to bring a joy or satisfaction
- Feeling a need to withdraw and/or spending an increased amount of time alone

If you believe you are experiencing these symptoms, engage in self-care, and discuss it with your clinical supervisor.

Note. Adapted from Evans (2015).

Acute Self-Care

Some situations (e.g., not hearing back from a student you were concerned for) may require you to engage in more acute self-care strategies. These may involve:

- Seeking further supervision from your clinical supervisor
- Engaging in discussion with your allocated buddy and your peers
- Team debriefing about the event and reflective space
- Engage in self-care strategies that you know are helpful for you
- Engaging in various resources and services, including Lifeline and university-specific services depending on what can best support you
- Monitor yourself and be aware of your personal warning signs that may indicate you need further support

The COMPAS team will support you and encourage you to attend to your mental wellbeing. Additional ways in which the COMPAS team can support you, if you wish, involve:

- Nominated peer-support person
- Confidential reflective space
- Ability to arrange a group reflective session
- Additional training and role-plays
- Supportive adjustments of your workload

If you would like to partake in these, please discuss with the clinical team

Absences

If you are unwell and unable to attend a shift, you must contact the clinic lead or Project Manager as soon as possible. If contacting by email, flag as 'high priority' ("!").

Supervision

Each university will have its own process for supervision, but in general:

Group supervision will be available on a regular basis (e.g., fortnightly via WebEx or another platform).

Ad hoc supervision can be accessed as needed—for example, to debrief after a difficult call, check clinical decision-making in a high-risk situation, or review documentation.

For urgent matters, follow your university's escalation process. If your primary supervisor is unavailable, contact another supervisor from the provided list.

For non-urgent matters that require attention before the next scheduled supervision, send a text or email to your designated supervisor, who will arrange a time to follow up as soon as possible.

Always err on the side of caution—reach out if you need support.

Confidentiality

Before any clinicians can access student, information or make a call, a confidentiality agreement needs to be completed and signed. This will be covered under the confidentiality agreement you sign for your internal placement.

All Master students are expected to act in accordance with the APS Code of Ethics. *Notably, you can freely discuss issues when talking to other members of the COMPAS team who are covered by confidentiality agreements.* However, if you are talking to others outside of the COMPAS project (e.g., peers, students, family, friends) you can talk about the project as a concept but not about any of the calls you have had.

Requirements to participate in COMPAS

All clinicians will require the following forms before they commence any work related to COMPAS including:

- Enrolled in an APAC-accredited psychology course
- Enrolment within a practical placement

This ensures all students will have the requisite basic training, police checks, working with children checks (if applicable), and training in ethical conduct.

Glossary of Terms

These are commonly used terms used within this guide. The terms highlighted are words that may have different meanings to the way they are typically used.

Term	Meaning
Acute	Denoting conditions or symptoms of sudden onset, short duration, and often great intensity
At-risk student	A student with much higher than average chance of experiencing suicidal ideation or attempts within the following 12 months
BeyondBlue	An Australian mental health and wellbeing support organisation with resources to support individuals with depression and anxiety
BeyondNow	An app and online website through Lifeline to support people struggling with suicidal thoughts by creating a safety plan
CAP plan	A document that outlines adjustments recommended for a student with a disability/medical condition or a carer of a person with a disability to assist equitable access to their studies
Compassion fatigue	The emotional and physical erosion that occurs when an individual cannot refuel and regenerate
COMPAS	C hecking O n M ental H ealth: P roviding Alternatives to S uicide: a research-based program that identifies students at future risk of suicidal behaviour using a multivariable algorithm and proactively reaches out to assess needs and link with appropriate resources
Multivariable	Two or more variables
Person-centred	When the individual is at the centre of the service and is treated as a person first. Care is focused on each individual's needs.
Safety planning	A list of coping strategies, support, and resources an individual can use to help them in crisis or during a difficult time.
Self-care	The ethical and legal imperative to look after your physical and psychological wellbeing
Strengths focused	An approach that centres positive attributes (including capacity, skills, knowledge, connections, and potential), rather than deficits. Viewing individuals as resourceful and resilient in face of hardship
Suicidal ideation	A broad term that describes the thought processes or ruminations about ending one's life
Wellbeing check	A designated university team calling or visiting a student to assess their needs and offer support, following institutional guidelines
Vicarious trauma	The experience of trauma symptoms that can result from exposure to other individuals' trauma

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National Institute for Health and Care Excellence

Self-harm: Assessment, management and preventing recurrence

- historic factors, including but not limited to:
 - vulnerabilities, including those related to age, race, religion, gender identity, sexual orientation, linguistic and cultural factors
 - past self-harm and/or suicidal behaviours
 - adverse childhood events
 - history of trauma, if the person feels able to discuss this in the acute context
 - family history of suicide
 - any mental health and/or neurodevelopmental condition and its relationship to self-harm
 - treatments
- changeable and current factors, including but not limited to:
 - recent and current life difficulties
 - recent or ongoing trauma
 - ability to engage in work or educational activities
 - methods and frequency of current self-harm, including their ongoing access to methods of self-harm
 - prescribed medicines
 - current suicidal thoughts and behaviours
 - significant relationships and changes to them
 - threats of abuse or harm (see Evidence report C on consent, confidentiality and safeguarding)
 - the needs of any dependents and any safeguarding issues
 - harmful or hazardous use of alcohol or recreational drugs
 - any personal, financial, social or other factors preceding self-harm, such as emotional distress
 - the benefits and harms of social media and internet resources
- future factors, including specific upcoming events or circumstances
- protective or mitigating factors, including but not limited to:
 - coping strategies (social, psychological, pharmacological) that the person has used to:
 - limit or avert self-harm **or**
 - minimise the impact of personal, social or other factors preceding episodes of self-harm
 - supportive personal and family relationships
 - support from statutory or third sector services
 - the person's and their family and carers' (as appropriate) perspective about their ability to manage their distress.

Information Sheet

HREC Project Number:	HRE2024-0356 COMPAS: Checking On Mental health, Providing
Project Title:	Alternatives to Suicide
Principal Investigator:	Prof Penelope Hasking

values the mental health and well-being of its students, and encourages all students to complete this wellbeing check.

What's involved?

This involves completion of a **20-40 minute** online survey, which will ask you questions about your past and current experiences, your physical and mental health, whether you have ever used mental health services, experiences of suicidal thoughts and behaviours. We will also ask about coping strategies you use and social supports you have in place. Finally, with your consent we will access your grades so we can see if our program is associated with retention and academic performance. You can still participate in the program even if you do not wish us to access your grades. If you are not comfortable answering a certain question, feel free to skip that question. Your participation will help us develop effective prevention and early intervention programs for students, ensuring University students are mentally healthy and more easily able to achieve their potential.

What are the benefits and risks?

Participating in this survey will help us develop effective prevention and early intervention programs for students. Your contributions will play a crucial role in creating a supportive environment that ensures university students are mentally healthy and better equipped to achieve their potential.

However, there are some risks to be aware of. Reflecting on past experiences related to mental health, substance use, emotional problems, and self-harm may cause emotional distress. If any questions are uncomfortable, you may skip them and you are able to stop the survey at any time. We understand that discussing personal experiences can be challenging, and support resources are available to access here as well as at the end of the survey.

What if I'm having trouble coping at the moment?

You might find some of the following resources helpful:

University Specific Security Contact Details (Specific to each university)

Lifeline – Call 13 11 14 for 24 Hour Crisis Support and Counselling

University Counselling Centre – Provides Free Counselling Sessions for all Students (Specific to each university)

BeyondNow – A Free Suicide Safety Planning App

Beyond Blue – Website with Information and Resources for Enhancing Mental Health

[\\${e://Field/Curtin%20Resource%20Link}](#)

Who will have access to my responses?

If you report suicidal behaviour in the last 12 months, or members of our research team at Curtin University believe your responses on the survey suggest you are at elevated risk of suicidal behaviour, one of our clinical trainees at Curtin University will use the contact details you provide to contact you (via your preference of a phone call or text message conversation) to see how you are going. If we are unable to get in touch with you after 3 attempts, we will pass your contact information onto the Safer Community Team, who may try to get in contact with you to make sure you are safe. This could include visiting your home if they have not been able to reach you or ensure your safety another way. Only your contact details (not your survey responses) will be provided to Safer Communities if we feel it is necessary.

Curtin University is partnering with COMPAS Ltd – a not for profit company that oversees this project. The main role of COMPAS Ltd is to oversee the operations of the project, including the phone system we use. For this reason, your name and phone number will be sent to the phone system at COMPAS Ltd so that clinicians at Curtin University can follow-up your call. No survey responses or any other information will be sent to COMPAS Ltd. The Directors of COMPAS Ltd are all part of the Curtin research team. Only the Curtin University research team will have access to any information you provide, and this will be de-identified for data storage and analysis. Nothing you say in this survey will ever be passed on to anyone at the university (e.g. tutors, lecturers).

In order to meet their registration requirement, clinical trainees must undergo formal supervision by a registered supervisor. As such, each member of our clinical team is supervised by an experienced clinical psychologist. For training purposes, and to meet supervision requirements, this senior psychologist may be on the line for some of the phone calls. You will always be given the option to decline to have the supervisor present.

In the instance that your survey responses suggest that you are at elevated risk of suicidal behaviour and you prefer being contacted via text message, your messages will be saved on our secure system as case notes for our clinicians to be able to refer to and provide the best help possible.

What's next?

We will invite you to complete a similar follow-up survey each year throughout your degree, so that we can see how you are going and support your university journey. We will also invite you to share your thoughts about this initiative and how you think your university should value student mental health.

Consent, Confidentiality, and Use of Data

Your participation in this initiative is entirely voluntary. Data collected over the course of your participation in this initiative will be stored in accordance with Curtin University regulations,

kept on University premises, in a password-protected file for at least 7 years. Data you provide in this study may be used in future research or by Curtin University for program planning purposes. In future, de-identified data may be compared to similar data collected at other universities around the world.

We will collect your name and email address to contact you if you win our prize draw. This information will make your data briefly identifiable. However, once the prize draw is complete, we will remove all identifying details from the data. The de-identified data will then be used solely for analysis purposes and stored securely at Curtin University. We will not have any way to link the de-identified data back to you.

Reimbursement:

For each round of surveys, all participating students will be offered the opportunity to win a \$50 gift voucher (four per participating university, per survey). Upon completion of the survey, you will be automatically entered into the competition. Two weeks after the survey closes, we will use a random number generator to pick four winners from the completed entries. <https://www.random.org/> will be used to complete the random selection. Winners will be notified within 7 days of the draw.

Funding:

This project is funded by The National Health and Medical Research Council (NHMRC, in conjunction with Beyond Blue, Lifeline WA, Headspace and the Office of Medical Research and Innovation at the Government of Western Australia Department of Health.

Contacts and Accessibility:

We are committed to ensuring that this survey is accessible to everyone, including individuals with disabilities. If you encounter any difficulties in accessing or completing the survey, please contact us at COMPAS-S@curtin.edu.au. We will be happy to provide assistance or alternative formats upon request. If you have any other questions or would like more information, please contact our team at: COMPAS-S@curtin.edu.au

All research in Australia involving humans is reviewed by an independent group of people called a Human Research Ethics Committee (HREC). The ethical aspects of this research project have been approved by the Curtin University HREC (HRE2024-0356)

ethics@curtin.edu.au. This project will be carried out according to the National Statement on Ethical Conduct in Human Research (2007). If you have any concerns and/or complaints about the project, the way it is being conducted or your rights as a research participant, and would like to speak to someone independent of the project, please contact: The Curtin University Ethics Office by telephoning 9266 2784 or by emailing hrec@curtin.edu.au

Your consent

Remember, taking part in this study is your choice. You may choose not to be in the study or to stop being in the study at any time for any reason. This will not affect your class standing or any other status or services at your University.

Your consent:

Yes I consent to participate in the project No, I don't consent to participate in the research project (end of survey)

Consent to link your survey responses with administrative grade records.

Yes, I consent the researchers confidentially accessing my grades to match with my survey responses for research purposes

No, I don't consent the researchers confidentially accessing my grades to match with my survey responses

Consent to link your survey responses with records of your enrolment status at University i.e., whether or when you leave University)

Yes, I consent the researchers confidentially accessing details about my length of time at University to match with my survey responses for research purposes

No, I don't consent the researchers confidentially accessing details about my length of time at University to match with my survey responses

CRM Contact Record

Hide Details

Task Information

Task Owner	Secretary COMPAS	Contact	Daniel Marsh
Due Date	26/03/2025	Subject	Initial Contact
Status	Not Started	Priority	High
Account	University	Closed Time	—
Created By	Secretary COMPAS Wed, 26 Mar 2025 08:38 AM	Modified By	Secretary COMPAS Wed, 26 Mar 2025 08:38 AM
Reminder	—		

Call/SMS Note-Taking Template

Communication Form	—	Call answered?	—
If Yes, Consent to talk now?	—	If No, leave a message	—
Limits of confidentiality	—	If No, did student agree to any further communication	—
If Yes, agreed date/time of callback/text conversation	—	If No, reason student declined communication	—

Risk Assessment

Purpose of call	—
Risk assessment completed	—
No (why not? Detail below)	—
Risk Level	—

Safety/Coping Plan

Which plan was chosen ? @	—
Student agreed to collaborate on the plan	—
(If Yes, detail plan below. If No, detail further)	—
Recommendations and actions taken	—
Any resources already accessed	—
Coping strategies	—
Any resources suggested	—

Acceptability

How helpful have you found our discussion today?	—
--	---

Further actions required

1-month follow-up scheduled?	—
Action not taken	—
Rationale	—
Additional Info	—

Consultation with Supervisor(s)

Who	—	Date/Time	—
Outcome	—		

Ensure that you have completed the below

Attached the safety management plan to the CRM	—
Deleted safety management plan from the computer?	—

Description Information

Description	—
-------------	---

Click here to access templates

send SMS

Large empty text area for composing a message.

Text Message [Send icon]

From:

Templates

send SMS

Prepopulated templates available here

General Follow-Up Offering a Time Window

Emphasising Flexibility Reach Out Filler Message 1

Filler Message 2 Filler Message 3 Confidentially

Hi %First_Name%, this is [NAME] from COMPAS. I tried calling you today but wasn't able to get through. Let me know a good time to call, or if you'd prefer, you can reply to this message. You can also find more information and resources here: <https://www.compas.org.au/resourcespage> .

Select Update

Call/SMS Note-Taking Template

Choose the send mail either in the students account or in the task

Use the drop down menu to choose the COMPAS email address when emailing students